

VALIDATED SPECTROSCOPIC METHOD FOR ESTIMATION OF MIRABEGRON BULK DRUG AND ITS DOSAGE FORM

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ABSTRACT:

In this work, a straightforward, accurate, and precise UV spectroscopic method was developed and validated for Mirabegron using the hydrotrophy technique in both the pure and commercial formulation. Using urea as the solvent, the absorption maximum was found at 246.40 nm. At concentration ranges of 10-80 µg/mL and correlation values of 0.9992, it complies with Beer-Lambert's law. Less than 2% was found to be the percent RSD for both accuracy and precision. Findings indicated that the LOD and LOQ values were 0.99 µg/mL and 0.329 µg/mL. It was discovered that Mirabegron's percentage recoveries ranged from 99.76 to 104.20%. In accordance with ICH Q2 (R1) guidelines, the suggested method was validated. The developed method worked well for figuring out the dosage form and bulk drug of mirabegron.

KEYWORDS: Mirabegron, Urea, UV-Visible Spectrophotometer, Validation

INTRODUCTION: Mirabegron, a β₃-adrenergic receptor agonist, is authorized in the US, Europe, and Japan to treat OAB. [1&2] Second-line therapy options include oral anticholinergics and β₃-adrenergic agonists. [3] The use of β₃-adrenergic agonists has improved OAB therapy by reducing anticholinergic side effects. [4] Adverse symptoms of anticholinergics include dry mouth, impaired vision, and constipation [5], as well as an increased risk of falls [6]. Mirabegron was sold under the brand name “Myrbetriq”. Mirabegron, a β-3 adrenergic receptor agonist, was approved by the FDA in 2012 to treat OAB, relax detrusor smooth muscle during storage, and increase bladder capacity

(Zuchowski et al., 2022; Kuo and Kuo, 2023).Hydrotropic agents are used in the UV-visible spectrophotometric method to increase the drug's aqueous solubility. The drug, Mirabegron, is dissolved using the hydrotropic agent 0.1 M urea in the current procedure. Literature review of mirabegron reveals various spectroscopic methods like UV^[7-11], RP- HPLC^[12-17],and LC-MS/MS^[18] etc.

Fig: 1 Structure of Mirabegron

MATERIALS AND METHOD:

UV-visible spectrophotometer (Shimadzu UV-1800 model), sonicator(Sonica-mod.2200MH), weighing balance (Shimadzu AUX 220). Mirabegron bulk drug sample was obtained from MSN Laboratories Pvt Ltd (Hyderabad), Urea from Sd Fine Chem Ltd (Mumbai), Mirabig-s (25mg) tablets.

INSTRUMENTATION:

Fig:2 UV-Visible Spectrophotometer

UV-Vis spectrophotometry is a sophisticated analytical method for measuring light absorption across the ultraviolet (UV) and visible (Vis) ranges of the electromagnetic spectrum that is applied in many different scientific domains. A UV-Vis spectrophotometer measures the amount of light that enters a sample solution and compares that intensity to the light that was incident, providing important insights into the characteristics of materials and how they interact with light.

Fig:3 Wavelength Range of UV-Visible Spectrophotometer

PRINCIPLE OF UV SPECTROSCOPY The Principle of UV-Visible Spectroscopy is the idea that chemical compounds can absorb ultraviolet or visible light, creating distinct spectra in the process. The basis of spectroscopy is the interaction of light and matter. A spectrum is created when the substance absorbs the light through excitation and deexcitation processes. The electrons existing in matter experience excitation when it absorbs UV energy. As a result, they move abruptly from their ground state (an energy condition with a negligible amount of energy) to their excited state (an energy state with a relatively large amount of energy associated with it). It is significant to remember that the amount of ultraviolet or visible radiation absorbed by an electron is always equal to the energy difference between its ground state and excited state. The Beer-Lambert Law is the basic principle of absorbance spectroscopy. For a single wavelength, the following formulas are used: A = absorbance (unit less, commonly shown as arb. units or arbitrary units), a = molar absorptivity ($M^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$) b = path length of the cuvette or sample container (usually 1 cm), and c = concentration of the solution (M).

$$A = a b c$$

Where A: Absorbance, a: Absorptivity, b: path length, c: Concentration

$$C: A / a b$$

Components of a UV-Vis spectrophotometer

- **LightSource:** Provides ultraviolet and visible light. Common sources include deuterium lamps (for UV) and tungsten lamps (for visible light).
- **Monochromator:** Separates the broad spectrum of light from the source into its component wavelengths. It includes an entrance slit, a dispersing element like a prism or diffraction grating, and an exit slit to select a narrow band of wavelengths to pass to the sample.
- **Sample Holder:** A cuvette or cell that holds the sample solution. The material of the cuvette must be compatible with the wavelengths being used; quartz is often required for UV light because glass absorbs UV radiation.
- **Detector:** Measures the intensity of the light after it has passed through the sample. Common detectors include photomultiplier tubes (highly sensitive) and photodiode array detectors (PDA).
- **Data Recorder:** Records the measured light intensity and converts it into a meaningful output, such as absorbance or transmittance, often in the form of a spectrum.

Fig: 4 Single beam spectrophotometer

Fig: 5 Double beam spectrophotometer

EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURE:

Preparation of solvent (0.1 M Urea): Solvent was prepared by dissolving 600 mg urea in 100ml of distilled water to produce 0.1 M urea.

Standard stock solution: A stock solution containing 1000 $\mu\text{g/mL}$ of pure drug was prepared by dissolving an accurate amount of 25 mg of mirabegron pure drug in 25 ml of 0.1 M urea. 0.1 ml of the above solution was pipetted out and made up to 10 ml using urea to get a solution of 10 $\mu\text{g/mL}$.

Determination of λ_{max} : Above solution was scanned in the wavelength range of 200-400 nm using UV visible spectrophotometer. The absorption maximum was determined at 246.40 nm.

METHOD VALIDATION: The method was validated for linearity, accuracy, precision LOD and LOQ as per the ICH guidelines.

Fig: 6 Method Validation

LINEARITY:To prepare standard stock solutions of pure drug, 25 mg of drug was dissolved in 25 ml of 0.1 M urea to yield 1000 μ g/mL of Mirabegron. 10ml of the solution were prepared by taking 0.1ml from this one. In a similar manner, various concentrations between 10 and 80 μ g/mL were prepared. The UV spectrum was scanned using standard solutions. [19]

RANGE:The interval between the upper and lower levels (including these levels) that can be accurately, precisely, and linearly determined by following the written method is what is meant to be understood. The range is typically expressed in the same units as the test results that the analytical method yielded, such as percentages or parts per million.

ACCURACY:The methods accuracy was assessed by figuring out the recoveries of Mirabegron using the standard additions method. 80%, 100%, and 120% of pure Mirabegron bulk drug, were added to three separate 10 ml volumetric flasks. The remaining volume was then brought to the mark using 0.1 M urea. After further diluting the solution with 0.1 M urea, it was examined with 0.1 M urea serving as a blank. By measuring absorbance(246.40 nm for Mirabegron)the amount of Mirabegron was estimated. By estimating the drug in triplicate preparations of each designated concentration level, the recovery was confirmed.

PRECISION:Three estimates of the corresponding response were made for three different concentrations of Mirabegron (10, 20, and 40 μ g/mL) on the same day in order to determine the intra-day precision. By estimating the corresponding response three times on three separate days for the same concentrations of mirabegron using both methods, the inter-day precision was ascertained. Afterwards, the concentrations were computed using the regression equation that the linearity studies had produced.

LIMIT OF DETECTION (LOD) ANDLIMIT OF QUANTIFICATION (LOQ):The limit of detection (LOD) and limit of quantification (LOQ) for the procedure were performed on sample containing very low concentration of analyte (Mirabegron) under the ICH guidelines. From the linearity data, the limit of detection and quantification was calculated using the following formula.

$$\boxed{\text{LOD} = \frac{3.3 \sigma}{S}} \quad \boxed{\text{LOQ} = \frac{10 \sigma}{S}}$$

σ = Standard deviation of the curve, S = Slope of the curve

ANALYSIS OF COMMERCIAL TABLETS (ASSAY):

Preparation of sample: 20 Tablets were powdered. The powder equivalent to 25 mg of mirabegron was transferred to 25 ml volumetric flask and 25 ml of 0.1 M urea was added to dissolve mirabegron in it and filtered through Whatman filter paper. 0.2 ml of the filtered solution was diluted to 10 ml with 0.1M urea. The drug content was estimated from the absorbance value and the regression equation obtained for linearity studies.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION:

Calibration plot of Mirabegron: Mirabegron was showing linear relationship between concentration ($\mu\text{g/mL}$) and absorbance in the range of 10-80 $\mu\text{g/mL}$. From the linear regression analysis correlation co-efficient value was found to be 0.999 which indicates the linearity of the method. Calibration data was reported in table. It was observed that with the increase in Mirabegron concentration, the absorbance values at 246.40 nm were increased.

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S.No	Concentration ($\mu\text{g/mL}$)	Absorbance (AM) (n=3)
1	10	0.12
2	20	0.24
3	40	0.44
4	60	0.63
5	80	0.83

Table: 1 Linearity data

Fig:7 Overlay UV spectrum of Mirabegron (10-80 $\mu\text{g/mL}$)

Accuracy (Recovery studies): The standard addition method was used to determine the accuracy. In triplicate, three distinct standards (80%, 100%, and 120%) were spiked onto commercial tablets. Table 2 presents the mean percentage recoveries and percentage RSD

Formulation	Spiking Level (%)	Contents of Sample ($\mu\text{g/mL}$)	Content of std Spiked ($\mu\text{g/mL}$)	Total Conc. ($\mu\text{g/mL}$)	Conc. Recovered ($\mu\text{g/mL}$)	Recovery (%)	%RSD
Mirabegron	80	10	8	18	18.786 \pm 0.12	104.20	0.417
	100	10	10	20	20.593 \pm 0.35	102.96	1.69
	120	10	12	22	21.948 \pm 0.38	99.76	1.73

values. The results showed that the Mirabegron% recoveries fell between 99.76 and 104.20%, which is a satisfactory range.

Table 2: Accuracy of the method (Recovery Studies)

Acceptance criteria: %RSD should not be more than 2.

Figure 8: Calibration graph of Mirabegron by UV method

Precision: The repeatability (intra-day) of the method was determined by intra-day (n=3) analysis of three standard solutions of Mirabegron at the concentration of 10, 20 and 40

Parameters	Values
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$\mu\text{g/mL}$. The %RSD of repeatability was <2.0 for the drug. Intermediate precision was determined by the inter-day ($n=3$) analysis of three standard solutions of the drug. Values are given in table 3.

Mirabegron				
Concentration ($\mu\text{g/mL}$)	Intra-day precision		Inter-day precision	
	Concentration estimated ($\mu\text{g/mL}$) ($n=3$)	%RSD ($\text{AM}\pm\text{SD}$)	Concentration estimated ($\mu\text{g/mL}$) ($n=3$)	%RSD ($\text{AM}\pm\text{SD}$)
10	10.1 \pm 0.1	0.99	10.23 \pm 0.26	0.73
20	20.25 \pm 0.25	1.23	20.28 \pm 0.28	0.60
40	40.23 \pm 0.20	0.51	40.38 \pm 0.34	1.04

Table 3: Precision of the method

LOD and LOQ:

LOD AND LOQ of Mirabegron were calculated and the values are tabulated in the table 4.

S.No	Validation parameter	Value(mg/mL)
1	LOD	0.329
2	LOQ	0.99

Table 4: LOD and LOQ values

Analysis of commercial tablets (Assay):

Assay of Mirabegron tablets (Mirabig tablets – 25 mg) drug was performed by using UV spectrophotometry and the percentage purity was found to be 98.75%.

λ max(nm)	246.40 nm
Beers Law limits ($\mu\text{g/mL}$)	10-80
Regression equation (Y)	$Y=1.0024x + 0.031$
Slope (m)	1.0024
Intercept (C)	0.031
Correlation coefficient (r ²)	0.9992
Limit of Detection ($\mu\text{g/mL}$)	0.329
Limit of Quantitation ($\mu\text{g/mL}$)	0.99

Table 5: Optical characteristics of Mirabegron

CONCLUSION:

UV spectroscopy, sometimes referred to as ultraviolet-visible spectroscopy, is a method for examining how a sample absorbs or transmits ultraviolet or visible light. Because of its affordability, speed, and ease of use, it is frequently employed in pharmaceutical analysis. UV spectroscopy is frequently used for quantitative analysis in the context of chromatographic techniques, where the concentration of a compound in a sample is ascertained by its absorption of UV or visible light. For the analysis of Mirabegron, a hydrotrophy-based UV spectroscopic technique has been developed. The ability of some substances, referred to as hydrotropes, to make poorly soluble compounds more soluble in water is referred to as hydrotrophy. In this procedure, hydrotrophy is used to increase Mirabegron's solubility and facilitate UV spectroscopy analysis. ICH established guidelines for the validation of the developed method. In order to make sure that an analytical method is accurate, repeatable, and reliable, validation is a crucial step in the process. The parameters typically assessed during validation include linearity, accuracy, precision, limit of detection (LOD), and limit of quantification (LOQ). The method was found to be linear in the range of 10-80 $\mu\text{g/mL}$. % RSD for accuracy and precision was found to be less than 2. LOD and LOQ values were found to be 0.329 and 0.99 $\mu\text{g/mL}$. The assay values were found to be in good agreement and the % purity was found to be in the range of 98.75 %.

The validation results for the Mirabegron UV spectroscopic method are reported as satisfactory, indicating that the method meets the required criteria for analytical performance. Specifically, the method demonstrates good linearity, accuracy (closeness of results to the true value), precision (repeatability and intermediate precision), and sensitivity (as indicated by low LOD and LOQ values). One notable advantage of the developed method is the absence of organic solvents in the sample preparation process. Instead, a 0.1 M urea solution is used for preparing stock solutions and dilutions.

This strategy adheres to the concepts of green chemistry and lowers costs while also improving the method's environmental friendliness. All things considered, the hydrotropy-based UV spectroscopic method provides a useful and affordable way to analyze mirabegron in pharmaceutical formulations. Because of its validation, which guarantees the accuracy of the results, it can be used for regular quality control procedures in pharmaceutical labs.

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